

'Green future' versus 'Planetary boundaries'? Evolving online discourse coalitions in European bioeconomy conflicts

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ABSTRACT

The European Commission is pursuing a circular bioeconomy to tackle pressing sustainability challenges, such as climate change and fossil dependency. Previous bioeconomy policy studies demonstrated the existence of competing bioeconomy discourses in the European Union. However, it remains nebulous how such discursive conflicts emerge and change, particularly in online settings. In this paper, we provide a more in-depth analysis of how argumentative changes of actors alter the network of online dynamic discourse coalitions. We base our findings on interviews and a qualitative discourse network analysis of 9983 tweets about European Union bioeconomy policies from the period 2008–2021. Our results indicate that initially, expert debates centred around storylines on bioeconomy advantages. After the 2012 Bioeconomy Strategy, the debate diversified with the entry of new actors and storylines. Two discourse coalitions, 'Green future' and 'Planetary boundaries', emerged around conflicting storyline clusters. In the aftermath of the 2018 Bioeconomy Strategy update, the debate simplified into core argumentations of few, highly conflicting storylines, leading to a polarization of the two discourse coalitions. Storyline hijacking further added to polarization and conflict. Understanding the evolution of online dynamic discourse coalitions provides new opportunities for practitioners to open up discourses towards storylines from other parts of the discourse network. This can help to prevent locking-in the limited range of solutions in congruence with the dominant 'Green future' discourse.

1. Introduction

Policymakers in the European Union (EU) have pursued a circular bioeconomy (CBE) to address pressing sustainability challenges, such as climate change and the dependency on fossil resources (European Commission, 2018; Kardung et al., 2021; Temmes and Peck, 2019). A bioeconomy is 'an economy where the basic building blocks for materials, chemicals and energy are derived from renewable biological resources, such as plant and animal sources' (McCormick and Kautto, 2013, p. 2590). The CBE concept connects the bioeconomy with circularity principles, such as waste minimalization and the prolongment of the value retention of products (cf. D'Amato et al., 2017). In the European Union, moving towards a *sustainable* and *circular* bioeconomy is cherished for marrying economic benefits (e.g., limiting the dependency on fossil raw materials, providing new markets for EU-based businesses, and maintaining the EU's global competitiveness) with ecological ones

(e.g., climate neutrality and limiting waste) (European Commission, 2018; Meyer, 2017; Priefer et al., 2017).

Critics, however, stress that realizing a CBE may further increase the demand for bio-based resources (e.g., crops, wood, or algae), at the detriment of already overused ecosystems (Kleinschmit et al., 2017; Riemann et al., 2022). Since sustainably sourced bio-based resources are not abundant, different uses (most prominently, food, materials, and energy) may compete for resources, such as land, water, capital, and labour (Muscat et al., 2020). While these concerns might be addressed by establishing a use hierarchy (Muscat et al., 2021) and limiting the resource base for industrial production to waste streams, more fundamental questions remain. These fundamental questions centre around the sustainability and circularity of bio-based production. For instance, it is doubted whether energetic uses of biomass actually reduce greenhouse gas emissions (Korhonen et al., 2018; Zabaniotou, 2018). Moreover, a CBE as envisioned by EU policymakers may solidify problematic

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power relations by focusing on value-added products in the formal market, while disregarding informal practices, such as food self-provisioning (Pungas, 2023). Biophysical constraints limit the scale of a CBE, because an absolute decoupling of value generation and resource consumption is thermodynamically impossible (Giampietro, 2019; Vivien et al., 2019). Focusing on substituting the raw material base from fossil-to bio-based without addressing the demand side therefore contributes to manifesting unsustainable scales of consumption in some parts of the globe and resulting global justice issues (Ramcilovic-Suominen and Püzl, 2018).

Social scientists studying bioeconomy and circularity debates have analysed how different actor groups argumentatively promote conflicting bioeconomy or circularity discourses and associated courses of action (e.g., Bugge et al., 2016; Dieken and Venghaus, 2020; Giurca and Metz, 2018; Kleinschmit et al., 2017; Leipold, 2021; Meyer, 2017; Ramcilovic-Suominen and Püzl, 2018; Riemann et al., 2022; Vogelpohl, 2021). Central topics in these discursive struggles are the expected sustainability of bio-based resources and the roles of technological versus other forms of innovation in the transition towards a CBE (Priefer et al., 2017). Scholars have shown that the dominant discourse in EU bioeconomy policymaking argues that technological innovation enables a substitution of fossil raw materials by bio-based resources to maintain current consumption levels; an alternative discourse highlights that the CBE is limited by planetary boundaries, with the consequence that other transition pathways need to be explored (Pungas, 2023; Ramcilovic-Suominen et al., 2022; Ramcilovic-Suominen and Püzl, 2018; Riemann et al., 2022).

Previous CBE research has successfully identified competing discourses and surrounding actor coalitions in EU bioeconomy politics, but the analytical focus was less on how these discourses came into being and how they might change. The broader literature on discursive change, however, suggests that both the constellation of discourse coalitions and the stories they tell may evolve over time, calling for a specific analytical focus on such discursive dynamics on the level of individual actors (e.g., Metz and Dodge, 2016; Starke et al., 2022; Yuana et al., 2020). Moreover, previous CBE studies have largely focused on academic debates or the policy process, drawing on academic literature (Bugge et al., 2016; Vogelpohl, 2021), survey data (Giurca and Metz, 2018), or policy documents (Kleinschmit et al., 2017; Meyer, 2017; Ramcilovic-Suominen and Püzl, 2018), occasionally combined with stakeholder interviews (Leipold, 2021; Riemann et al., 2022). Research into the larger public debate, for instance in online settings, is still in its infancy. Therefore, the research gap is that it remains unclear what discursive dynamics, on the level of individual actors, underlie the emergence of the two competing discourses in EU bioeconomy policymaking in online settings. We address this gap by posing the research question: *How have discourse coalitions evolved in online EU bioeconomy debates?* In this study, we are particularly interested in the role of social media platforms, as these have become an important arena for public debates (Marres, 2015; Stevens, 2020; Teixeira Rabello et al., 2021). X, the social media platform formerly known as Twitter, constitutes such a public arena that is widely used by both interested citizens and official organizations (cf. Gu et al., 2016; Stevens, 2020).

We approach our research question by advancing the conceptualization of discourse coalitions as dynamic and emerging both off- and online. Discourse coalitions do not only change because new actors embrace already existing discourses. Rather, actors add and alter storylines and thereby change the discourses themselves. In this paper, we further conceptualize and empirically study how such argumentative changes reshape connections between actors around shared discourses. Our contribution is that we specify how argumentative changes of individual actors continuously alter the network structure of their discourse coalitions. Understanding how this network of discourse coalitions changes is relevant because dominant understandings become institutionalized in policies and regulations (Fischer, 2003; Hajer, 1995), ultimately shaping the actions of societal actors. Closing down

ideas in policy debates to dominant understandings (Stirling, 2008) holds the danger of generating discursive lock-ins, which are situations where one understanding is so dominant that policymakers do not take into consideration innovations stemming from another discourse (Metz, 2018; Simoens et al., 2022; Simoens and Leipold, 2021). Such a situation limits the search for innovative policy approaches (Brown and Dillard, 2015). For instance, a focus on technological innovation for stimulating the valorisation of bio-resources might impede social innovations to reduce the demand for materials and energy (Vivien et al., 2019).

We base our results on the qualitative analysis of the content of 9983 tweets on EU bioeconomy debates in the period 2008–2021, spanning the elaboration of current EU bioeconomy policies. We identified changes in discourse coalitions by conducting a discourse network analysis (DNA) (Leifeld, 2013, 2017; Leifeld and Haunss, 2012). DNA is currently predominantly used to map advocacy coalitions around the shared agreement or disagreement on policy instruments (Leifeld et al., 2022). We contribute to further broadening the DNA application range towards tracking evolutions of discourse coalitions by redefining concept nodes as storyline nodes and omitting the dis-/agreement qualifier. Our adaptations avoid the ‘bipolarization by design’ problem (Leifeld, 2017, p. 5) when using DNA to track discourse coalitions.

The paper proceeds by providing a theoretical background on discourse theory, highlighting the currently rather static understanding of discourse coalitions in previous social sciences contributions to the CBE literature. Based on this, we present a more dynamic understanding, drawing on the literature on discursive dynamics. After outlining our material and methods and clarifying our methodological adaptations, we present our results. This paper ends with a discussion of our findings, including implications for bioeconomy policymaking.

2. Theoretical background

Identifying discursive changes in online debates over time requires a more dynamic understanding of discourse coalitions. In this section, we first provide a background on discourse theory. Second, we synthesize how previous social science contributions to the CBE literature have so far approached discursive changes in a rather static manner. Third, we build on the discursive change literature to arrive at a more dynamic understanding.

2.1. Discourses and discourse coalitions

Previous social science contributions to the CBE literature have identified competing discourses on the bioeconomy in the EU (e.g., Kleinschmit et al., 2017; Ramcilovic-Suominen et al., 2022; Ramcilovic-Suominen and Püzl, 2018; Vogelpohl, 2021). In this study, we follow Hajer (1995, p. 44) in defining *discourses* ‘as a specific ensemble of ideas, concepts, and categorizations that are produced, reproduced, and transformed in a particular set of practices and through which meaning is given to physical and social realities’.

Actors do not act in isolation, but form groups around shared discourses, so-called *discourse coalitions*. Discourse coalitions are ‘the ensemble of (1) a set of story-lines [as communicated representations of discourses]; (2) the actors who utter these story-lines; and (3) the practices in which this discursive activity is based’ (Hajer, 1995, p. 65). A storyline is a ‘generative sort of narrative that allows actors to draw upon various discursive categories to give meaning to specific physical or social phenomena’ (Hajer, 1995, p. 56). In contrast to advocacy coalitions, in which actors form coalitions around shared interests (Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith, 1993), a discourse coalition is formed around implicitly or explicitly shared storylines. Hence, in understanding how policies change, the discourse coalition conceptualization emphasizes the role of discursive changes, rather than changes in actors and institutions (Fischer, 2003). Discursive changes institutionalize into policymaking because policymakers regard some problem definitions

and policy options as suitable in accordance with their discursive categories, while disregarding others (Hajer, 1995). Changing these discursive categories results in a different array of regarded problem definitions and solutions.

A related, but somewhat different concept is the *discourse network*. A discourse network is a 'cross-sectional clustering of actors around similar statements' (Leifeld, 2017, p. 5). Such statements are utterances of actors with reference to an idea (Leifeld, 2017). While a discourse coalition describes groups around shared ideas, the discourse network refers to the entirety of discourses and actors present in a debate, clustered according to their congruence. Hence, different discourse coalitions can be part of the discourse network. Moreover, discourse networks differ from discourse coalitions because actor practices and congruent ideas, which are not uttered, are not considered as part of the discourse network.

2.2. Understandings of discourse coalitions in the CBE literature

Despite valuable insights into existing bioeconomy discourses, previous CBE studies have predominantly approached discourse coalitions as rather static groups around stable storylines. For example, Vogelpohl (2021) studied transnational sustainability certification schemes for biomass. He identified a discourse coalition of industry and national state actors opposing these schemes. However, the study did not aim to provide insights into changes in this discourse coalition. Giurca and Metz (2018) conducted a network analysis of actors around similar visions of the wood-based bioeconomy in Germany, similarly as Mijailoff and Burns (2023) for Argentina and Uruguay. Findings concern a particular moment in time, with the development of the network falling outside the scope of both studies. Riemann et al. (2022) analysed the argumentation of non-governmental organizations (NGOs), identifying a static narrative of a fixed group. Dieken and Venghaus (2020) identified changes of what actors refer to the visions identified by Bugge et al. (2016), while adaptations of these visions over time are not regarded. Consequently, the analytical focus so far lies on changes in what actors align with what discourse on what moment in time and to a lesser extent on changes in the discourses themselves.

As a notable exception, Leibold (2021) identified a 'change coalition' (p. 5) around environmental actors promoting radical waste reduction policies and a 'status quo coalition' (ibid.) around industry actors opposing these policies. Later, the European Commission worked towards bringing actors together in a 'joint coalition' (p. 6) that strived to *redefine* the initial storyline. While providing an analysis of discursive changes in circularity policies, the study did not focus on bioeconomy policies. Moreover, it remained outside that study's scope how actors within one discourse coalition alter storylines and how this affects the composition of their discourse coalition.

2.3. Towards a more dynamic understanding of discourse coalitions

To move beyond current static understandings, discourse coalitions need to be approached as inherently dynamic, paying attention to how actors continuously work on shaping their storylines (Metze and Dodge, 2016; Starke et al., 2022). Over time, actors strengthen storylines, for example by gathering new empirical material to underline the validity of a narrative (confirmation), establishing new connections between storylines (integration), contesting storylines (disintegration), and reconfirming differences between different storylines (polarization) (Metze and Dodge, 2016, p. 4).

We build on this understanding by further specifying how individual actors continuously reshape their discourse coalitions through storyline adaptations. Termeer (1993) identified different patterns of how network configurations of actors change when involved actors adjust their definitions of social reality. This implies that actions of individual actors can lead to shifts in the relational network of their groups. Actors evolve their argumentation over time. These storyline adaptations result

in shifts in both the internal composition and the relational network structure of discourse coalitions. Due to storyline adaptations, other actors may start contesting the adapted storyline and ultimately 'leave' a discourse coalition, start a new one, or 'join' another one. Consequently, discourse coalitions can shrink, grow, solidify, merge, fall apart, disappear, or (re)appear over time.

3. Material and methods

We analysed how the discourse network evolved on X between August 2008 and June 2021. This time period entails the elaboration of the first EU Bioeconomy Strategy in 2012 and its update in 2018. For our analysis, we adapted an established approach to identify discourse networks, discourse network analysis (Leifeld, 2013; Leifeld and Haunss, 2012). We combined this discourse network identification with an interpretive analysis of the content of tweets spread through the discourse network, based on an inductively constructed coding scheme. An extensive research protocol is provided as supplementary material.

3.1. Data set construction

To identify the online discourse network, we created a data set of tweets by applying the search string (*biomass OR bioeconomy*) AND (*'European Union' OR EU*). By choosing these key words, the data set focuses on bioeconomy and biomass debates, with less emphasis on neighbouring debates (such as circularity or air pollution). The initial data set consisted of $N = 39,930$ tweets.

We reduced the data set by selecting the most impactful tweets. On X, users can like, retweet, or quote-retweet content to show their appreciation, comment their dissent, and further disseminate tweets to their own followers. For selecting the most impactful tweets, we ranked them from the highest to lowest total number of retweets, likes, and quote-retweets per tweet, with the highest ranking to be considered most impactful. We set a threshold of 25 per cent most impactful tweets per year to be included in the analysis. This reduced the data set to manageable proportions ($N = 9983$) for a manual, in-depth qualitative analysis. These tweets form the analysed network for this study. We maintained the time stamp of every tweet to allow for a longitudinal analysis.

3.2. Adaptations of the discourse network analysis method

Some adaptations of the DNA method were needed to allow for a more dynamic analysis of evolving discourse coalitions. In DNA, two types of nodes are used: actor and concept nodes (Leifeld, 2013). Actor nodes represent actors in a data set, in our case user accounts. Concept nodes represent arguments or ideas in a debate (Leifeld, 2017). These nodes are connected by edges, which can be visualized as links in a network graph. Edges can be qualified as either an agreement or disagreement relationship between an actor and a concept node. This qualifier introduces a binary variable into the data set: clusters of actors form around either the agreement or disagreement on a set of concepts. For this specific study, we adapted the DNA in two ways.

As a first adaptation, we redefined concept nodes into storyline nodes (cf. Kukkonen et al., 2021). While concept nodes in DNA usually refer to ideas in a broader sense, in our adaptation, storyline nodes stand for an opinionated, generic narrative, highlighting particular aspects of social reality.

A second adaptation is that we only used agreement qualifiers and no disagreements. Hence, all actor-storyline connections were coded as agreement. We did so for a conceptual and a methodological reason. Conceptually, actors in discourse coalitions rather deploy alternative storylines instead of solely disagreeing with a storyline. Methodologically, omitting the dis-/agreement qualifier avoids the 'bipolarization by design' problem (Leifeld, 2017, p. 5), describing a design-induced trend towards bipolar network structures in using DNA to identify discourse

coalitions. A bipolar network structure displays two discourse coalitions, based on either agreement or disagreement of actors on a set of policy instruments in line with their endorsed discourse. Omitting the dis-/agreement qualifier allows for the identification of complex structures of multiple discourse coalitions, highlighting various storyline combinations.

3.3. Interpretive analysis to establish storyline nodes

To establish storyline nodes, we performed a manual interpretive analysis of the storylines that are used in EU bioeconomy debates. To this end, we first constructed an initial list of controversial aspects in bioeconomy debates and connected storylines highlighted by the existing literature (e.g., [Leipold, 2021](#); [Ramcilovic-Suominen and Püzl, 2018](#); [Temmes and Peck, 2019](#); [Vogelpohl, 2021](#)) and eight experts from the European Commission, NGOs, and industry associations, who we interviewed between June and September 2021. We used this list as an initial coding scheme for storyline nodes.

We then took samples from our data set to iteratively adapt the initial coding scheme. To this end, the first author performed two training rounds of coding in the Discourse Network Analyzer software ([Leifeld et al., 2019](#)) on randomly selected quarters of the data set. After each round, we refined the coding scheme. Questionable cases and coding scheme adjustments were discussed among the team of authors to establish a common set of storylines and to enhance coding reliability. Examples of storylines coded for are ‘Green growth’ (a CBE is an environmentally friendly way to maintain or increase economic growth), ‘Sustainability criteria’ (certification schemes or guarantees of origin are needed to ensure the sustainable harvesting of bio-resources), and ‘Deforestation overseas’ (increased demand for bio-resources in the EU leads to deforestation elsewhere). Annex A includes the final list of storylines and their definitions.

3.4. Analysis of discourse coalition dynamics in three time periods

To analyse dynamics of discourse coalitions over time, we split the data set into three time periods according to changes in EU bioeconomy policies, see [Fig. 1](#). Period 1 spans from the first available tweet on 13 August 2008 until the publication of the first EU Bioeconomy Strategy on 13 February 2012. Period 2 ranges until the publication of the strategy’s update on 10 October 2018. Period 3 runs until the last included tweet from 30 June 2021.

For each of the three periods, we extracted two types of networks: actor and storyline congruence networks. In *actor congruence networks*, actor nodes are connected by an edge if accounts deploy statements with reference to a common storyline. In resulting network graphs, edge

Fig. 1. Number of tweets and statements per year in the three periods.

weight indicates the number of statements with shared storylines between actors ([Leifeld et al., 2019](#), p. 9). These networks visualize the (unintentionally) formed groups of actors around congruent storylines. In this analysis, we regard actor clusters around a coherent combination of storylines as discourse coalitions. We also extracted *storyline congruence networks* (cf. [Kukkonen et al., 2021](#); [Leifeld, 2017](#)), in which we checked what storylines are commonly referred to by actors. We present storyline congruence network graphs as supplementary material.

4. Results

Discursive dynamics and changing compositions of online discourse coalitions over time are presented over three time periods, corresponding with EU bioeconomy policy changes.

4.1. Period 1 (2008–2012): Expert debate highlighting different positive bioeconomy effects

Period 1 spans from the start of available tweets in August 2008 until the publication of the first EU Bioeconomy Strategy in February 2012. This strategy sketched a ‘knowledge-based bioeconomy’ ([European Commission, 2012](#), p. 18). Bioeconomy advantages were seen in benefits for economic growth and rural development, while greening primary production and lowering the dependency on fossil raw materials.

In the first period, we observe a multifocal debate, with multiple actor clusters interpreting the topic slightly differently. Specific discourses are not visible, yet. A central ‘Green future’ cluster involved industry actors, experts from the European Commission, and journalists, see [Fig. 2](#). According to this cluster, bio-technological innovation would decouple economic growth from environmental impacts. Actors of this cluster were tightly connected to the ‘Sustainability criteria’ cluster, which broadly endorsed the storylines of ‘Green future’ but specified the need for sustainability criteria for bio-resources.

Around these central clusters, several smaller clusters nuanced this ‘Green future’ narrative, for example by adding the element of a particular opportunity for peripheral regions (‘Rural development’ cluster). A ‘Planetary boundaries’ cluster of non-governmental

Fig. 2. Actor congruence network for period 1. Nodes represent actors, their colours indicate different actor categories. Selected node labels are displayed. Node size is proportional to the frequency of statements the actor made. Edge weight indicates the strength of congruence, with the highest 5% visualized in black, 5–20% in dark grey and below that in light grey. Light blue group nodes indicate actor clusters. Grey curved boxes display cluster labels, storylines characterizing the cluster and the total number of utterances of these storylines.

organizations (NGOs) and citizen accounts pointed out that not every form of biomass use was CO₂-neutral. Moreover, they criticized the role of genetic engineering as a bioeconomy enabler.

4.2. Period 2 (2012–2018): Diversification and formation of a counter-coalition

Period 2 consists of the period between the Bioeconomy Strategy and its update in October 2018. A participation process preceded this update, in which the European Commission invited interested persons and organizations to submit position papers. In the updated strategy, the bioeconomy concept was explicitly married with the concepts of sustainability and circularity.

After the publication of the 2012 Bioeconomy Strategy, the discourse network diversified. While industry actors, university professors, environmental NGOs, and some European Commission experts participated in period 1, new discussants in period 2 included members of the European Parliament, member state organizations, journalists, and other citizens.

Parallel to the diversification, the network constellation became more bipolar, see Fig. 3. Instead of several connected clusters that broadly share the same discourse, two main discourse coalitions emerged in period 2. First, a ‘Green future’ coalition of industry and European Commission actors integrated storylines that were shared by separate clusters in period 1. This coalition considered a global, large-scale bioeconomy, enabled by technological innovation, as inherently circular due to the use of renewable resources. Second, a ‘Planetary boundaries’ coalition, mostly consisting of environmental NGOs, criticized the vision of a bioeconomy set out in the 2012 strategy. For instance, this coalition questioned the assumed carbon-neutrality of bio-resources due to the long time period until emitted carbon is bound back. A bioeconomy would make things worse by further contributing to deforestation and biodiversity loss.

4.3. Period 3 (2018–2021): Simplification and increasing polarization

Period 3 ranges from the strategy’s update until the end of the data set in June 2021. In this period, the European Green Deal was published, which further stressed sustainability principles in developing the bioeconomy, for instance highlighting reforestation (European Commission, 2019, p. 13) and rural development (p. 23). The Fit-for-55 package to deliver the Green Deal’s climate ambitions does not entail the term bioeconomy, but calls for a ‘green, competitive, inclusive, circular economy’ (European Commission, 2021, p. 12).

After the Bioeconomy Strategy’s update, storyline clusters simplified. Most statements of both discourse coalitions concerned the simplified question of whether or not the bioeconomy in general functions to mitigate climate change by binding more carbon than it emits, regardless of whether energy or more durable products are produced. The ‘Green future’ coalition now focussed on storylines to underline that developing a bioeconomy would be necessary to achieve policy goals, such as global climate commitments or the EU Green Deal. The ‘Planetary boundaries’ coalition stopped broadly uttering the consolidating ‘Not all biomass is CO₂-neutral’ storyline and focussed on more fundamental concerns. A bioeconomy would mean more harm than good by adding more CO₂ and other pollutants due to additional production, transport, and harvesting as well as endangering biodiversity by stimulating deforestation.

Congruent to this simplification, the discourse network further polarized into a bipolar structure, see Fig. 4. While actors in the overlap of the two coalitions were still present in period 2, the overlap nearly vanished in period 3.

Compared to period 2, many EU-funded research projects joined the ‘Green future’ coalition. Projects, for instance Bloom or Schoolnet, integrated the storylines ‘Education’, ‘Public awareness’, and ‘Democratization’ into a common narrative. According to this narrative, a bioeconomy would be fostered by empowering the younger generation to discuss the future of the bioeconomy as well as informing the public about how a bioeconomy benefits society.

5. Discussion and concluding remarks

This paper started with the aim of developing a better understanding of discourse coalition dynamics in online EU bioeconomy debates. While our findings confirm the general divide between an ecomodernist and an ecological discourse coalition in bioeconomy politics, as recently identified in Europe (Ramcilovic-Suominen et al., 2022) and South America (Mijailoff and Burns, 2023), our contribution is that we point out the dynamics underpinning the emergence of these two coalitions online. Initially, primarily experts participated in the online debate, which diversified towards the broader public after the adoption of the 2012 EU Bioeconomy Strategy. This diversification involved the entry of new actors and storylines into the discourse network. Besides the emergence of new storylines brought in by new actors, debates also simplified into two main argumentations. On the one side, the ‘Green future’ coalition argued that a bioeconomy was a necessity to achieve climate goals and EU Green Deal objectives. On the other side, the ‘Planetary boundaries’ coalition scrutinized the assumed carbon neutrality and highlighted environmental trade-offs. The diversification towards the broader public

Fig. 3. Actor congruence network for period 2. The highest 5% of congruence values are visualized by black edges. Edges with lower congruence values are not displayed, nor are isolates.

Fig. 4. Actor congruence network for period 3. The highest 5% of congruence values are visualized by black edges. Edges with lower congruence values are not displayed, nor are isolates.

and the simplification of storyline clusters contributed towards an increasing *polarization* of the debate, resulting in a bipolar discourse network with tight internal links and few connections between the coalitions.

This sequence of dynamics at the level of the discourse network is grounded in storyline adaptations by individual actors, which [Metze and Dodge \(2016\)](#) identified as storyline integration, disintegration, confirmation, and polarization. While the debate diversified, established actors confirmed storylines, resulting in the growth of actor clusters and tighter links within a corresponding storyline cluster. For example, in period 2, the congruence between the ‘Circularity’ and ‘Green growth’ storylines in the ‘Green future’ cluster increased compared to period 1. Actors worked towards a simplification of the debate by disintegrating storylines of another discourse coalition and integrating complex storylines into a simple core argumentation. As a result of this simplification, debates centred around few, highly conflicting storylines. Nuanced and consolidating storylines shifted towards the periphery of the discourse network. This loss of nuance risks simplifying bioeconomy debates into black-and-white clashes on the energetic use of biomass, possibly constraining deliberations on less straightforward trade-offs, such as lock-ins, but also consolidating options, such as use hierarchies.

In addition to the dynamics proposed by [Metze and Dodge \(2016\)](#), we suggest storyline hijacking as an additional dynamic leading to polarization and conflict escalation. Hijacking means integrating a storyline from another discourse coalition, but redefining it to match one’s own interpretation of reality (cf. [Vivien et al., 2019](#)). For example, the ‘Green future’ coalition seems to have hijacked storylines such as ‘Circularity’. While environmental organizations initially stressed that a bioeconomy is *not* inherently circular, ‘Green future’ actors claimed that a bioeconomy is inherently circular, because it uses renewable resources. As a result of storyline hijacking, actors have different interpretations in mind when referring to the same storyline. Conflict smoulders in this.

While proving useful to track storyline dynamics over time, our study also has limitations. Notably, the analysed debate on X is only part of the public debate ([Stevens, 2020](#)). DNA studies traditionally rely on newspaper articles (e.g., [Kukkonen et al., 2021](#); [Leifeld, 2013](#); [Mijailoff and Burns, 2023](#)). However, we find that tweets are particularly useful for DNA because tweets are coherent and short. Actors selectively highlight aspects that they find most important. Moreover, tweets can univocally be connected to one actor by the user handle and have a time stamp. Using different textual data might result in the identification of different discourse coalitions. Therefore, it cannot be inferred that the same coalitions would also appear in different settings, for instance in public consultation processes.

Moreover, our analysis does not allow for conclusions about how balanced the online debate is, because we regarded uttered storylines as equally valid, thus independent of their scientific substantiation. To mitigate a false balance bias in our interpretation, we grounded our analysis in standing literature and interviews with experts from different perspectives.

Our findings have implications for the literature on EU bioeconomy policymaking. In particular, results indicate the starting institutionalization of a discursive lock-in towards the ‘Green future’ understanding. If powerful decisionmakers gather on one side of the discourse network and alternative discourse coalitions are excluded from this idea-policy channel, then policymakers face a bias in the range of considered policy options ([Metze, 2018](#); [Simoens et al., 2022](#); [Simoens and Leipold, 2021](#)). This discursive lock-in of the ‘Green future’ discourse has started to institutionalize, because EU-funded research projects gather exclusively in the ‘Green future’ discourse coalition. EU-funded research projects thereby perpetuate the dominant discourse, which limits the disruptive potential of innovation to techno-economic solutions. This is problematic, because the range of regarded policy solutions and envisaged futures ([Ahola-Launonen and Kurki, 2022](#)) becomes biased towards the ones congruent with the ‘Green future’ discourse. Future

research can further explore how this bias in considered problem definitions and solutions becomes legislation and how this affects the development of bioeconomy projects on the ground.

At the same time, our results are in line with findings that argumentations within one discourse coalition are not as unified and stable as the discursive divide suggests ([Eckert, 2021](#)). In fact, we show that actors continuously adapt their storylines. Discourses are therefore evolving and changeable. To unlock the current discursive lock-in, recent bioeconomy policy research has suggested more inclusive, participatory approaches in governing the bioeconomy, for example in crafting regional bioeconomy strategies ([Szarka et al., 2023](#)). Our findings suggest that this focus on inclusivity in bioeconomy governance needs to be accompanied by a focus on the plurality of involved knowledge systems and fundamental perspectives (see also [Gebara et al., 2023](#)). Future work remains to design models of participatory bioeconomy governance that not only foster inclusivity, but also plurality.

In addition, our findings have governance implications. First, our findings imply that a further politicization of debates on the future of the bioeconomy is required to surface the biases in problem definitions and connected solutions that result from the discursive congruence of EU decisionmakers and EU-funded research projects with industrial actors. In funding decisions and policymaking, the danger smoulders of exclusively aligning research and policies with techno-economic perspectives, which are congruent with the ‘Green future’ discourse. This could contribute to a further decline of the disruptive character of research and innovation (see [Park et al., 2023](#)) and failing to deliver the bioeconomy’s transformative ambition by a perpetuation of unsustainable business practices ([Eversberg et al., 2023a](#); [Lühmann and Vogelpohl, 2023](#)). To surface these value conflicts, it is necessary to politicize currently rather technical bioeconomy debates ([Eversberg et al., 2023b](#)). Policymakers and stakeholders engaging in the debate can work on this in both offline and online settings.

Second, our longitudinal analysis enables understanding at what moments and due to what argumentative changes the debate closed down, which also allows for the identification of entry points to open up the debate again. Regarding these moments as intervention points enables more adaptive governance by avoiding locking-in problem definitions and solutions congruent with one particular – and changing – discourse. Practitioners can work towards opening up the debate by including storylines from different parts of the discourse network. For instance, the Joint Research Centre published a report on alternative bioeconomy visions, which also highlights problem definitions congruent with the ‘Planetary boundaries’ discourse ([Giuntoli et al., 2023](#)). This helps in avoiding a bias towards problem definitions and solution approaches in congruence with the ‘Green future’ discourse in bioeconomy policymaking.

Third, policymakers should embrace the innovative potential of conflicts to surface currently disregarded problem definitions and policy options. This implies that conflict and polarization are not necessarily bad news ([Cuppen, 2012](#)). Unlocking the innovative potential of conflicts requires stepping out of one’s own discursive bubble and seeking discussions with critics, even if this sparks disagreement ([Van Eeten, 1999](#)). A practical example is the ‘Beyond Growth’ conference in May 2023, organized by members of the European Parliament and also featuring critical voices of current EU policies. This includes establishing and maintaining relationships with stakeholders from other parts of the discourse network, which might form blind spots for policymakers tightly aligned with another part of the discourse network. Our findings imply that discourses and connected coalitions continuously change. Stakeholder identification and relationship forming must therefore be continuous processes ([Cuppen, 2018](#); [Wehling, 2012](#)).

Taken together, a bioeconomy with sustainability and circularity at its heart requires considering problem definitions and solution approaches beyond the current bias towards dominant ‘Green future’ interpretations, which are only one side of the discourse network. In order to achieve this, policymakers, researchers, and other practitioners need

to work towards opening up bioeconomy debates to ideas from other parts of the discourse network.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jan R. Starke: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Tamara A.P. Metzke:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Jeroen J.L. Candel:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Art R.P.J. Dewulf:** Investigation, Resources, Data curation. **Katrien J.A.M. Termeer:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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References

- Ahola-Launonen, J., Kurki, S., 2022. Dynamics of expectations in the bioeconomy—hopes, disillusionments, and conflicting futures. *Sci. Publ. Pol.* 49 (6), 819–829. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scac030>.
- Brown, J., Dillard, J., 2015. Dialogic accountings for stakeholders: on opening up and closing down participatory governance. *J. Manag. Stud.* 52 (7), 961–985. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joms.12153>.
- Bugge, M.M., Hansen, T., Klitkou, A., 2016. What is the bioeconomy? A review of the literature. *Sustainability* 8 (7), 691. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8070691>.
- Cuppen, E., 2012. Diversity and constructive conflict in stakeholder dialogue: considerations for design and methods. *Pol. Sci.* 45, 23–46. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11077-011-9141-7>.
- Cuppen, E., 2018. The value of social conflicts. Critiquing invited participation in energy projects. *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 38, 28–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2018.01.016>.
- D'Amato, D., Droste, N., Allen, B., Kettunen, M., Lähtinen, K., Korhonen, J., Leskinen, P., Matthies, B.D., Toppinen, A., 2017. Green, circular, bio economy: a comparative analysis of sustainability avenues. *J. Clean. Prod.* 168, 716–734. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.09.053>.

- Dieken, S., Venghaus, S., 2020. Potential pathways to the German bioeconomy: a media discourse analysis of public perceptions. *Sustainability* 12 (19), 7987. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12197987>.
- Eckert, S., 2021. Varieties of framing the circular economy and the bioeconomy: unpacking business interests in European policymaking. *J. Environ. Pol. Plann.* 23 (2), 181–193. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2021.1894106>.
- European Commission, 2012. Innovating for sustainable growth: a bioeconomy for Europe. <https://doi.org/10.2777/6462>.
- European Commission, 2018. A sustainable bioeconomy for Europe: strengthening the connection between economy, society and the environment—updated bioeconomy strategy. <https://doi.org/10.2777/792130>.
- European Commission, 2019. The European green deal. <https://doi.org/10.2775/97540>.
- European Commission, 2021. Fit for 55—delivering the EU's 2030 climate target on the way to climate neutrality. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52021DC0550>.
- Eversberg, D., Holz, J., Pungas, L., 2023a. The bioeconomy and its untenable growth promises: reality checks from research. *Sustain. Sci.* 18 (2), 569–582. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-022-01237-5>.
- Eversberg, D., Koch, P., Lehmann, R., Saltelli, A., Ramcilovic-Suominen, S., Kovacic, Z., 2023b. The more things change, the more they stay the same: promises of bioeconomy and the economy of promises. *Sustain. Sci.* 18, 557–568. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-023-01321-4>.
- Fischer, F., 2003. *Reframing Public Policy: Discursive Politics and Deliberative Practices*. Oxford University Press.
- Gebara, M.F., Ramcilovic-Suominen, S., Schmidlehner, M.F., 2023. Indigenous knowledge in the amazon's bioeconomy: unveiling bioepistemicide through the case of kambo medicine. *For. Pol. Econ.* 154, 103012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2023.103012>.
- Giampietro, M., 2019. On the circular bioeconomy and decoupling: implications for sustainable growth. *Ecol. Econ.* 162, 143–156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2019.05.001>.
- Giuntoli, J., Oliver, T., Kallis, G., Ramcilovic-Suominen, S., Monbiot, G., 2023. *Exploring New Visions for a Sustainable Bioeconomy* (JRC132650). Joint Research Centre. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/79421>.
- Giurca, A., Metz, T., 2018. A social network analysis of Germany's wood-based bioeconomy: social capital and shared beliefs. *Environ. Innov. Soc. Transit.* 26, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2017.09.001>.
- Gu, Y., Qian, Z., Chen, F., 2016. From Twitter to detector: real-time traffic incident detection using social media data. *Transport. Res. C Emerg. Technol.* 67, 321–342. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trc.2016.02.011>.
- Hajer, M.A., 1995. *The Politics of Environmental Discourse: Ecological Modernization and the Policy Process*. Oxford University Press.
- Kardung, M., Cingiz, K., Costenoble, O., Delahaye, R., Heijman, W., Lovrić, M., Van Leeuwen, M., M'Barek, R., Van Meijl, H., Piotrowski, S., Ronzon, T., Sauer, J., Verhoog, D., Verkerk, P.J., Vracholi, M., Wesseler, J.H.H., Zhu, B.X., 2021. Development of the circular bioeconomy: drivers and indicators. *Sustainability* 13 (1), 413. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13010413>.
- Kleinschmit, D., Arts, B., Giurca, A., Mustalahti, I., Sergeant, A., Pülzl, H., 2017. Environmental concerns in political bioeconomy discourses. *Int. For. Rev.* 19 (1), 41–55. <https://doi.org/10.1505/146554817822407420>.
- Korhonen, J., Honkasalo, A., Seppälä, J., 2018. Circular economy: the concept and its limitations. *Ecol. Econ.* 143, 37–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.06.041>.
- Kukkonen, A., Stoddart, M.C., Ylä-Anttila, T., 2021. Actors and justifications in media debates on Arctic climate change in Finland and Canada: a network approach. *Acta Sociol.* 64 (1), 103–117. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0001699319890902>.
- Leifeld, P., 2013. Reconceptualizing major policy change in the advocacy coalition framework: a discourse network analysis of German pension politics. *Pol. Stud. J.* 41 (1), 169–198. <https://doi.org/10.1111/psj.12007>.
- Leifeld, P., 2017. *Discourse network analysis: policy debates as dynamic networks*. In: Victor, J.N., Lubell, M.N., Montgomery, A.H. (Eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of Political Networks*. Oxford University Press.
- Leifeld, P., Gruber, J., Bossner, F.R., 2019. Discourse network analyzer manual, september 11, 2019. <https://github.com/leifeld/dna/releases>.
- Leifeld, P., Haunss, S., 2012. Political discourse networks and the conflict over software patents in Europe. *Eur. J. Polit. Res.* 51 (3), 382–409. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-6765.2011.02003.x>.
- Leifeld, P., Henrichsen, T., Buckton, C., Fergie, G., Hilton, S., 2022. Belief system alignment and cross-sectoral advocacy efforts in policy debates. *J. Eur. Publ. Pol.* 29 (8), 1225–1248. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13501763.2021.1945131>.
- Leipold, S., 2021. Transforming ecological modernization 'from within' or perpetuating it? The circular economy as EU environmental policy narrative. *Environ. Polit.* 30 (6), 1045–1067. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2020.1868863>.
- Lühmann, M., Vogelpohl, T., 2023. The bioeconomy in Germany: a failing political project? *Ecol. Econ.* 207, 107783. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2023.107783>.
- Marres, N., 2015. Why map issues? On controversy analysis as a digital method. *Sci. Technol. Hum. Val.* 40 (5), 655–686. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0162243915574602>.
- McCormick, K., Kautto, N., 2013. The bioeconomy in Europe: an overview. *Sustainability* 5 (6), 2589–2608. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su5062589>.
- Metze, T., 2018. Framing the future of fracking: discursive lock-in or energy degrowth in The Netherlands? *J. Clean. Prod.* 197, 1737–1745. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.04.158>.
- Metze, T., Dodge, J., 2016. Dynamic discourse coalitions on hydro-fracking in Europe and the United States. *Environmental Communication* 10 (3), 365–379. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17524032.2015.1133437>.

- Meyer, R., 2017. Bioeconomy strategies: contexts, visions, guiding implementation principles and resulting debates. *Sustainability* 9 (6), 1031–1062. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9061031>.
- Mijailoff, J.D., Burns, S.L., 2023. Fixing the meaning of floating signifier: discourses and network analysis in the bioeconomy policy processes in Argentina and Uruguay. *For. Pol. Econ.* 154 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2023.103039>.
- Muscat, A., De Olde, E.M., De Boer, I.J.M., Ripoll-Bosch, R., 2020. The battle for biomass: a systematic review of food-feed-fuel competition. *Global Food Secur.* 25 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfs.2019.100330>.
- Muscat, A., de Olde, E.M., Ripoll-Bosch, R., Van Zanten, H.H.E., Metzke, T.A.P., Termeer, C.J.A.M., van Ittersum, M.K., de Boer, I.J.M., 2021. Principles, drivers and opportunities of a circular bioeconomy. *Nature Food* 2, 561–566. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-021-00340-7>.
- Park, M., Leahy, E., Funk, R.J., 2023. Papers and patents are becoming less disruptive over time. *Nature* 613, 138–144. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-05543-x>.
- Priefer, C., Jörissen, J., Frör, O., 2017. Pathways to shape the bioeconomy. *Resources* 6 (10), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.3390/resources6010010>.
- Pungas, L., 2023. Invisible (bio)economies: a framework to assess the ‘blind spots’ of dominant bioeconomy models. *Sustain. Sci.* 18, 689–706. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-023-01292-6>.
- Ramcilovic-Suominen, S., Kröger, M., Dressler, W., 2022. From pro-growth and planetary limits to degrowth and decoloniality: an emerging bioeconomy policy and research agenda. *For. Pol. Econ.* 144, 102819 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2022.102819>.
- Ramcilovic-Suominen, S., Pülzl, H., 2018. Sustainable development—a “selling point” of the emerging EU bioeconomy policy framework? *J. Clean. Prod.* 172, 4170–4180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.12.157>.
- Riemann, L., Giurca, A., Kleinschmit, D., 2022. Contesting the framing of bioeconomy policy in Germany: the NGO perspective. *J. Environ. Pol. Plann.* 24 (6), 822–838. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2022.2071689>.
- Sabatier, P.A., Jenkins-Smith, H.C., 1993. *Policy Change and Learning—An Advocacy Coalition Approach*. Westview Press, Inc.
- Simoens, M.C., Leipold, S., 2021. Trading radical for incremental change: the politics of a circular economy transition in the German packaging sector. *J. Environ. Pol. Plann.* 23 (6), 822–836. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2021.1931063>.
- Simoens, M.C., Leipold, S., Fuenfschilling, L., 2022. Locked in unsustainability: understanding lock-ins and their interactions using the case of food packaging. *Environ. Innov. Soc. Transit.* 45, 14–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2022.08.005>.
- Starke, J.R., Metzke, T.A.P., Candel, J.J.L., Termeer, C.J.A.M., 2022. Conceptualizing controversies in the EU circular bioeconomy transition. *Ambio* 51, 2079. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-022-01730-2>. –2090.
- Stevens, T.M., 2020. *Social Media Dynamics in Agro-Food Governance. Hypes, Emotions and Master Terms*. Dissertation Wageningen University. <https://doi.org/10.18174/514608>.
- Stirling, A., 2008. “Opening up” and “closing down”: power, participation, and pluralism in the social appraisal of technology. *Sci. Technol. Hum. Val.* 33 (2), 262–294. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0162243907311265>.
- Szarka, N., García Laverde, L., Thrän, D., Kiyko, O., Ilkiv, M., Moravčíková, D., Cudlínová, E., Lapka, M., Hatvani, N., Koós, Á., Luks, A., Martín Jimenez, I., 2023. Stakeholder engagement in the Co-design of regional bioeconomy strategies. *Sustainability* 15 (8), 6967. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15086967>.
- Teixera Rabello, E., Gommeh, E., Benedetti, A., Valerio-Ureña, G., Metzke, T., 2021. Mapping online visuals of shale gas controversy: a digital methods approach. *Inf. Commun. Soc.* 25 (15), 2264–2281. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2021.1934064>.
- Temmes, A., Peck, P., 2019. Do forest biorefineries fit with working principles of a circular bioeconomy? A case of Finnish and Swedish initiatives. *For. Pol. Econ.* 110, 101896 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2019.03.013>.
- Termeer, C.J.A.M., 1993. *Dynamiek en inertie rondom mestbeleid: Een studie naar veranderingsprocessen in het varkenshouderijnetwerk [Dynamics and inertia around manure policy: A study of change processes in the pig farming network]*. Dissertation Erasmus University Rotterdam. VUGA.
- Van Eeten, M.J.G., 1999. *Dialogues of the Deaf. Defining New Agendas for Environmental Deadlocks*. Eburon Publishers.
- Vivien, F.-D., Nieddu, M., Befort, N., Debref, R., Giampietro, M., 2019. The hijacking of the bioeconomy. *Ecol. Econ.* 159, 189–197. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2019.01.027>.
- Vogelpohl, T., 2021. Transnational sustainability certification for the bioeconomy? Patterns and discourse coalitions of resistance and alternatives in biomass exporting regions. *Energy, Sustainability and Society* 11 (3), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13705-021-00278-5>.
- Wehling, P., 2012. From invited to uninvited participation (and back?): rethinking civil society engagement in technology assessment and development. *Poiesis Praxis* 9 (1–2), 43–60. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10202-012-0125-2>.
- Yuana, S.L., Sengers, F., Boon, W., Hajer, M.A., Raven, R., 2020. A dramaturgy of critical moments in transition: understanding the dynamics of conflict in socio-political change. *Environ. Innov. Soc. Transit.* 37, 156–170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2020.08.009>.
- Zabaniotou, A., 2018. Redesigning a bioenergy sector in EU in the transition to circular waste-based Bioeconomy-A multidisciplinary review. *J. Clean. Prod.* 177, 197–206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2017.12.172>.